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VALUE BASED EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Values are essential for positive human behaviour. Education from time immemorial has focused on values. Values form the core of educational goals and objectives. Education is inherently values oriented and must develop in learners caring, co-operation and respect for others. In addition to equipping them with life skills and attitudes, it must prepare them to lead a full life.

A value is one of the many alternatives that a person chooses and acts upon because it increases human development. Values constitute that which is accepted by the group, community or society. Hence, all the aspects are important and linked to each other. Value means primarily to prize, to esteem, to appraise, to estimate, it means the act of cherishing something, holding it dear and also the act of passing judgment upon the nature and amounts of values as compared with something else.

Today there is deterioration of values in the society. The values have been neglected not only at the social level but at the national level also. There are several factors with the modern higher education which are making people literate or educated undoubtedly but on the other hand responsible for forgetting the basics or values of a good human being or a responsible citizen of the society.

In the existing educational system lays greater emphasis on individualism, competition, verbal fluency or linguistic ability and mere acquisition of information is given, this is just not sufficient and great emphasis will have to be given on the value education. Since it is the time to coherence with broadly acceptable national cultural identity where social values and development can be naturally reinforcing. The cultural values need to be identified for standard curricula all over the country. The value education should be imparted compulsorily up to the high school level. Evaluation of value education should be routine one and it should be based upon the daily observations of student by teachers and peers and should be monitored by administrator properly and also by the parents.

KEYWORDS: *human behaviour, essential, group, community or society*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the vehicle of knowledge, self-preservation and success. Education not only gives a platform to succeed, but also the knowledge of social conduct, strength, character and self-respect. The greatest gift education gives us is the knowledge of unconditional love and a set of values. These values include the simple difference between right and wrong, a belief in God, the importance of hard work and self-respect. Education is a continuous learning experience, learning from people, learning from leaders and followers and then growing up to be the person we are

meant to be. Value-based education is a threefold development of any individual of any gender and age, but most importantly of a child. Education tries to develop three aspects: physique, mentality and character.

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prepare them to lead a full life. As a society, the concern with Values Education is not unique to our times but the erosion of values has forced introspection and reflection in education. Values Education is integral to education of any kind and has been focused upon in many educational committee reports in India.

MEANING OF VALUE-EDUCATION

A value is one of the many alternatives that a person chooses and acts upon because it increases human development. Values constitute that which is accepted by the group, community or society. Hence, all the aspects are important and linked to each other. Value means primarily to prize, to esteem, to appraise, to estimate, it means the act of cherishing something, holding it dear and also the act of passing judgement upon the nature and amounts of values as compared with something else. A value stands for ideas men live for.

Value literally means something that has price, something precious, dear and worthwhile; hence something one is ready to suffer and sacrifice for; if necessary one is ready to die for it. Values are standards, rules, criteria, attitudes, guidelines, desirable ideas, beliefs and important things, which play a crucial role in shaping the life of individuals. Values give direction and firmness to life. Human values are the principles, standards, convictions and beliefs that people adopt as their guidelines in daily activities.

According to C. V. Good "Value education is the aggregate of all the process by means of which a person develops abilities, attitudes and other forms of behaviour of the positive values in the society in which he lives."

According to John Dewey "Value primarily means to prize, to esteem, to appraise, to estimate, it means the act of cherishing something's, holding it dear and also act of passing judgement upon the nature and amounts of values as compared with something else".

Value education is education in the sense that it is education for 'becoming'. It is concerned with the development of the total personality of the individual-intellectual, social, emotional, aesthetic, moral and spiritual. It involves developing sensitivity to the good, the right and the beautiful, ability to choose the right values in accordance with the highest ideals of life and internalizing and realizing them in thought and action. As such the process calls into play all human faculties - knowing, feeling and doing. Not only should the learner be enabled to know the right and the good, but also to care, to feel the appropriate emotions, concern and commitment and exercise the will to do the right

thing. In other words, to 'value educate' is to develop rational critical thinking, to educate the emotions, to cultivate the imagination, to strengthen will and to train character of the learner.

NATURE OF VALUES

- Values relate to the aims of human life. For the achievement of aims, main frames certain notions and these notions are called values.
- Our conduct is motivated by our values.
- Values are masterminds which give direction to one's strivings. Values represent feelings, wants, interests, attitudes, preferences and opinions about what is right, just, fair or desirable.
- Value is the act of cherishing something. A person who values justice will spend a lot of energy in search for it.

Individuals singly and collectively assume one of the following four instances in their attempts to formulate or change values and value systems.

- In the manner of the deductive, they postulate that truth is known a priority and thus needs only to be uncovered, understood and applied.
- In the manner of the pragmatist they postulate that tradition constantly tested should guide human affairs.
- In the manner of existentialist they postulate that individual man works out his own values.
- In the manner of the Hegelian, they postulate that built into history is a dynamic force that guides human life.

TYPES OF VALUES

Generally, values may be classified as personal, social, moral, spiritual and behavioural values.

A. Personal Values

They refer to those, which are desired and cherished by the individual irrespective of his social relationship. The individual determines his own standards of achievement and attains these targets without explicit interaction with any other persons.

B. Social Values

Social values refer to those, which are oriented and concerning to society. These values are practiced because of our association with others. Unlike personal values, the practice of social values necessitates the interaction of two or more persons.

C. Moral Values

Moral values related to individual's character and personality conforming to what is right and virtuous. They reveal a person's self-control.

D. Spiritual Values

Spiritual values refer the perception of the 'within' in man. It arises from the inner depth dimension of man. It bestows the capacity to see the false as the false and the true as the true. It is the key to the integration of man. The ultimate ethical value is called spiritual value. Spiritual value is the awareness of itself.

E. Behavioural Values

Behavioural values refer to all good manners that are needed to make our life successful and joyous. These are the values, which are exhibited by our conduct and behaviour in our daily life. Behavioural values adorn our life and spread cordially friendliness.

VALUES AND VALUE BASED EDUCATION

The contents of education still belong to the past. Education suffers basically from what the report describes as the gap between its contents and living experience of its pupils between the system of values that it preaches and the goals set up by society, between its ancient curricula and the modernity of science. - Learning To Be (the Report of the International Commission)

Objectives of Value Based Education

The education reform document 'Challenges of Education' (1985) enlists the following value orientation objectives:

- Physical, intellectual and aesthetic development of personality.
- Inculcation of a scientific temper, and democratic, moral and spiritual values.
- Development of self-confidence of innovate and to face unfamiliar situations.
- Creation of awareness of physical, social, technological, economic and cultural environment.
- Fostering a healthy attitude to dignity of labour and hard work.
- A commitment to principles of secularism and social justice.
- A dedication to uphold the integrity and honour, and foster the development of the country.
- Promotion of international understanding.

Need for Value based Education

- Moral development

- Cultural development
- Development of wider attitude
- Development of democratic qualities
- Sublimation of instincts
- Resolving conflicts
- Co-operative living
- Basis of humanitarianism
- Decoration of soul
- Maintaining harmony

Purpose of Value based Education

"The purpose of value-oriented education is to fight obscurantism, religious fanaticism and violence and promote and nurture critical thinking, reflection, reasoning and build-up a humane approach to life", National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), Director J.S. Rajput was quoted as saying in a statement.

Some basic Issues of Value based Education

There are certain age old traditions such as preference for the male child, notional advantages of a large family, religion as the sole guiding principle in personal and social life, caste as identity, etc. There is another set of values relating to attitudes and behaviour such as caring and sharing in the family and society, obedience and respect for elders, respect for argument and reasoning, non-violence and personal hygiene. In contemporary society, some of these values may need to be reinterpreted or replaced while some others may require reinforcement. In the context of these concerns, what values will reflect a national ethos?

- Very often, value oriented education and moral education are considered synonymous.
- How should education and school practices be kept apart from myths and beliefs?
- How should value oriented education be done? Can it be done through preaching religious and moral instructions?
- Should we consider a separate time slot for value oriented education or integrate values in education through teaching learning methods, instructional materials, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities.
- Very often there is a basic contradiction between what is in school and family as value oriented education and what children actually observe in society and through the media.

Value Based Education-Then and Now

A glance of philosophical, historical, political and social aspects reveal that there was a major shift of

value orientation from past to present due to many foreign invasions.

Ancient India was rich in spiritual and intellectual attainment. The ultimate objective of education was to equip the child for spiritual and moral life. Indian education has been considered to be not only intellectual pursuit but also a practical aid to show the right way of living. The unique feature of value system depicted in ancient Indian thought was that man was given freedom to acquire wealth (Artha) and physical well being (Kama) but it should be in a right way (Dharma) to attain ultimate goal of life (Moksha).

Value Based Education- Ancient India

Ancient Indian education was mostly value based and aimed to cultivate virtues in the form of ulterior values-truth (satyam), goodness (Sivam) and beauty (Sundaram). The ultimate purpose and aim of education in ancient India was self realization or divine perfection. Child was trained to control his desire and acquire skills required for self perfection in the past. He was initiated through a ritual, Upanayanam in order to attain self-perfection and knowledge. The relationship between teacher and taught was spiritual and divine. Teacher was an exemplary modern to students for imbibing noble values. The method of education involved three steps of Sravana (listening), Manana (deliberation) and Nididhyasana (meditation).

Value Based Education-Medieval and Modern India

The ultimate aim of education is to develop necessary skills, attitudes and values for meaningful and virtuous living in the changing society. It is due to scientific and technological development, man has shifted his way of living from spiritual to materialistic approach.

Value Based Education-21st Century

Every nation of the world is striving utmost to bring into the lives of their people, the marvels of science and technology. Now we are in fast changing worried world, ever sicken with fear of war annihilation. When we focus vision on India, the scenario is alarming. Materialism has engulfed us. Too much dominance of materialism in a country is leading to lack of faith in idealism. In the words of Prof.D.S. Kothari, science and technology are exploding but wisdom imploding. It is shrinking. Knowledge is expanding and human personality is shrinking. Because of the explosion of knowledge, we find various kinds of imbalances and calamities.

Value Based Education – Emerging Indian Society

The challenge before our country and all sections of our society is inculcation of ethical, social and spiritual values. The present malady in our society is the absence of ethical conduct. We have become slaves of material civilization. The dominant impulse of today is not only the greed for riches and desire for luxurious living but also desire for power by fair or foul means. How to give our society a worthy purpose motivated by ethics?

A national well being is in its spiritual and moral health. Everything else for which it strives depends on this. Our nation now requires the teachers of character, who possess a real sense of vocation. We still want all of them to assist in the task of “making good man and woman”. If value oriented education becomes a regular feature of school life, they could properly, increase the effectiveness of the school’s contribution to the value development of children.

The entire process of value oriented education is a highly complex process that involves a wide range and variety of learning experiences. Scholars and teachers have made their significant contribution towards value oriented education. They have provided ample opportunities for children to be aware to think and reflect, to question and criticize, to care and feel to develop the disposition and will to act on one’s convictions with references to critical human concerns. In the words of the Prof. S.R.Rotidekar, the success in value oriented education depends upon the enthusiasm and commitment of teachers and government. He emphasizes that, “the value oriented education is not an additional subject. It should permit all work and activities in education institutions like a guardian angel”. B.R. Gayal claims, one of the merging needs for school system is to plan for developing a definite outlook on values in students, teachers and parents. There is a need to create an educational climate through planning and organizing value oriented education strategies like the following

- ❖ Framing school policy on moral and social values.
- ❖ Announcing it to the pupils, parents and teachers.
- ❖ Creating a sense of feeling in teachers and parents for its implementation.
- ❖ Introducing the concepts through the school programs and classroom activities.
- ❖ Planning modification in organizational aspects of value oriented education policy.
- ❖ Reserving that value oriented education is the core of a school’s success.

CONCLUSION

Science and technology which is a great triumph for human kinds in this new era which makes human's life better and easier. Due to the gift of technologies, the world is connected and seems as one small city or village. People of this globe more voracious on material comfort which makes people's life more competitive. Hence, material wealth has become major indicator for measuring the success in every society instead of value based person. However, human's civilization fundamentally depends upon the cultivation of values, those values which shape human's lives and craft real human. Indeed, it is observed everywhere the values are degrading constantly which results increasing of inhuman activities. Thus; there is a great need for imparting value based education in each stage of education. Although education is an agent of change and the expected process of inculcating values to equip the learners for their successful life with the cherished values and contribute to ideal and healthy society.

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